

Matrix of Man

When Sibyl Moholy-Nagy published *Matrix of Man* in 1968, it was in a way the result of a life-long love affair with the great city. Her biography is punctuated by the names of great cities where she lived and worked: Berlin, Frankfurt, London, Chicago, New York. Especially this last city captured her imagination, as she dedicated *Matrix of Man* "To Manhattan, my inspiration and my love".

She expressed her love for the city already much earlier on, in 1954, when she wrote a statement for *Architectural Record*, entitled "Where the great city stands". "STADTLUFT MACHT FREI", she declared in this text ("the air of the city makes one free"), taking up the defense of all those who wished to live in a densely packed but dynamic and exciting city. She denounces those who have declared the city evil "from Ebenezer Howard to Frank Lloyd Wright, and from William Morris to Lewis Mumford." Whereas the "solution for man's happiness has been sought in green-belt towns and progressive suburbs, with man and community living in foolproof salubrity", she states that men nevertheless have continued to flock "to the airless, sunless, stone piles, suffering each other's proximity rather than that of the bird and the bee". She thinks that all those who want to solve the city's problems by planning satellites or garden cities have no real sense for what the city is all about. For the great city results from the fact that man does not live by sanitation alone: "There are and forever will be congenital city dwellers and congenital country dwellers, and no amount of sanitation in the broadest meaning of the word – sanitation of the soul and the body, so to speak – will make a country dweller out of a city dweller. There are millions of Americans, who (...) are bored by bridge and group television, and who do not want to bake cookies for the benefit of Girl Scouts. They hide behind the cold impersonality of a numbered apartment door not sinister tendencies, but the cherished right to be anonymous, to associate

not at all, or with unwanted minorities, to remain unquestioned about the time schedule of their waking hours, (...)"

At the time she is writing this article (1954) she is making her way as a professor of architecture at Pratt Institute in New York. Sibyl Moholy-Nagy was the second wife and biographer of Laszlo Moholy-Nagy, the famous artist and Bauhausprofessor. Born as the daughter of an architect in Dresden, Germany, she was active as an actress and scriptwriter before her marriage to Moholy in 1934. Throughout their marriage, she was involved in her husband's pedagogical undertakings in directing the New Bauhaus and later the Institute for Design in Chicago. After his death in 1946, she decided to become a professional teacher, establishing herself as an architectural historian in her own right. She managed to publish a huge amount of articles and a couple of books that made her very much present on the architectural scene, from the late fifties throughout the sixties (she died in 1971). Her first non-fiction book, which opened the gates to her career as a professor, was the biography of her late husband, *Moholy-Nagy. Experiment in Totality*. This book was published in 1950, four years after his death. Her next book, *Native Genius in Anonymous Architecture* (1957), was written after very demanding fieldwork which brought her across the American continent. In this publication she develops a series of arguments which some years later would make others famous: it anticipates indeed Rudofsky's *Architecture without Architects* (1964) and Rapoport's *House Form and Culture* (1969). The book presents vernacular architecture in America, which, she claims, has been ignored by architectural culture out of a misplaced disdain for local traditions. It discusses the factors of site and climate, of form and function, and of materials and skills. Its final chapter assesses "a sense of quality" which is present in this vernacular, but absent from the real estate developments that she sees booming all over the country. Her basic argument is: "To provide *the home as an ideal standard* is still the architect's first cause, no matter how great and rewarding are his other contributions to monumental and technological building. (...) As those builders of old, the architect of today has to create *an anonymous architecture for the anonymous men* of the Industrial Age." (Moholy-Nagy 1957, 23)

Unfortunately this book has never had the same impact as the later ones by Rudofsky and Rapoport. I would argue that this cannot possibly be for reasons of content. The book is well researched, well written, well illustrated. It wouldn't live up to scholarly standards of today, but the same can be said of Rudofsky and Rapoport. That it was almost ignored

might have to do with the fact that the book went very soon out of print, due to a reorganization of its publishing house, Horizon Press. It remains to be seen, however, in how far its author's rather ambivalent relationship with the old-boys-network that made up the architectural scene, has been an important factor in the process.

I do not exaggerate when I call her relationship with modern architects and modern architecture ambivalent. On the one hand she had lived very decisive years of her life – from 20 to 30 let's say – among avant-garde artists and filmmakers in Weimar Germany. Being married to Laszlo Moholy-Nagy meant she had the direct acquaintance of such men as Walter Gropius, Marcel Breuer or Sigfried Giedion. When she published the book on Moholy, it was with a very sympathetic and supporting foreword by Walter Gropius. She certainly shared a lot of ideas and ideals with her husband, whose intellectual legacy she continued to defend. On the other hand, however, it is gradually becoming clear from her writings that she show this legacy as one in the field of the visual arts, and that she did not extend her loyalty to the architecture that grew out of the Bauhaus. During the sixties she often criticizes modern architects, for celebrating technology and science at the detriment of human and urban values. In the article "Hitler's revenge", e.g., published at the eve of the coming out of *Matrix of Man*, she starts her argument in a most outspoken polemical tone:

"In 1933 Hitler shook the tree and America picked up the fruit of German genius. In the best of Satanic tradition some of this fruit was poisoned, although it looked at first sight as pure and wholesome as a newborn concept. The lethal harvest was functionalism, and the Johnnies who spread the appleseed were the Bauhaus masters Walter Gropius, Mies van der Rohe and Marcel Breuer."

This criticism culminates – though in a less polemical tone - in *Matrix of Man*. The book was published in 1968, from a manuscript she developed throughout the 60s during her teaching at Pratt, where she had a very successful course on the history of urban settlements. It was meant to be the first volume of a larger whole called *Canon of Architecture*, but her early death in 1971 prohibited the finishing of this largger project. We have MoM though and I must admit that I am particularly fond of the title. *Matrix*, my Webster's tells me means several things, a.o. "something that constitutes the place or point from which something else originates", "a formative tissue", "a mold for casting type faces". From other sources I have it to mean also womb or parent stem. By using the term *matrix* Sibyl

Moholy-Nagy clearly genders the city, qualifying it as a maternal body, giving life and nurturing man, while at the same time molding his form. As you might know the word has since been used often by feminists. *Matrix* was e.g. the name of an architectural feminist co-operative, working in London from 1980 onwards. *Matrix* is also a key-term for Brachta Lichtenberg Ettinger, the artist and psychiatrist. She relies upon this term to describe her specifically female approach to art and to the psyche, trying to get hold of this special relationship between I and nonI which is getting form through the womb.

These feminist overtones might not yet have been obvious when Moholy-Nagy chose *Matrix of Man* as the title for her book, but I am convinced that she was very conscious about the feminine connotations of the word. The title is well-chosen indeed, for it is her prime argument that the city is source and origin of civilization, and while it contains everything that is worthful in human culture it nurtures and gives form to the intellectual and emotional lifes of the individuals that live in it.

The book is constructed according to thematic categories. She discerns five basic concepts of human settlements, five patterns which form the *Gestalt* of cities: geomorphic, concentric, orthogonal-connective, orthogonal-modular and clusters. Geomorphic patterns are determined by the shape and the climatic conditions of the earth, they have an organic structure and are based upon an interaction with the landscape. They are the oldest ones found by archeologists, under the form of villages, rural towns or citadels. As the most impressive example of geomorphic planning she names Machu Picchu, which "achieves a total accord with the given environment because the sun worshipers conceived the city as a crown of nature, and nature as the crown of the city" (p. 28). But it is clear to her that geomorphic patterns continue to be of consequence throughout the history of human settlements, as e.g. in the military fortifications of Vauban. Moholy-Nagy indeed is convinced that these different patterns, although they may originate from different eras and places, are archetypes which continue to be of consequence in urban planning.

The second type she distinguishes are concentric settlements. They come forth from a commitment to a suprahumane ideal, from a tradition that conceives of the urban form as the superimage of the ideal self. This type was predominant in medieval cities, where the cathedral and other public buildings acted as the core of the concentric pattern. The concentric city offers an image of power, from which the influence of its ruler radiates over a vaster area. Its urban qualities derive from the interaction between public buildings and the more humble con-

structions that form their background. Moholy-Nagy discusses widely different examples, in which the configuration of public buildings is the most important urban feature: from the temple of Apollo at Delphi, the temple district of Jerusalem and the emperor's halls in Peking to the Maya city of Uxmal in Yucatàn, Mexico. According to her, the concentric strategy continues to play a role, just like the geomorphic approach. She recognizes it as well in the renaissance schemes of ideal cities as in the utopian images of the 19th and early 20th centuries, such as those by Ebenezer Howard.

Her treatment of the third and fourth type – orthogonal-connective and orthogonal-modular patterns – is less straightforward, for now she intermingle the thematic structure of the chapters of the book even more with a chronological narrative. This narrative starts with a discussion of proto-orthogonal concepts as found in Ancient Egypt or Babylon, and proceeds to deal with “the Greek wave” (a discussion of the influence of Alexander the Great and the Hellenistic urban tradition) in order to continue with “the Roman orbit” (the urban revolution brought about by imperial Rome in which “no longer did city make the ruler but the ruler made the city” (p. 101). Nevertheless two main ideas can be distilled from her account. First that the orthogonal-connective type is based on a desire for communication and very much linked to the impact of merchants who see the city as a place for commerce and connecting. The linear-connective pattern favours the linear street, the rectangular block, and public squares as urban determinants. Second that the orthogonal-modular type is based on the military logic of Roman camps. It is a grid based on uniform modules which add up in an endless continuation. In this type, Moholy-Nagy argues, streets are less lines of communication than dividers of lots, and public spaces are not designed environments but voids between housing modules. “In contrast to the other types of urban foundations,” she states, “the modular grid plan is not generated from within the community but is predetermined from without. To the genesis of urban intentions from rural (geomorphic) to cosmological (concentric) to ecumenical (orthogonal-connective), the modular grid adds a coercive concept, whether political or religiously motivated, imposing on plan, building and inhabitant the same predetermined dimensions.” (p. 158)

It is this orthogonal-modular type that according to her prevailed in the New World, because “To the founding fathers, land was a commodity to be sliced, weighed, and sold to the highest bidder. (...) It would take 200 years for the fugitives of millennia of urban tradition to acquire ‘city sense’ and by that time – our own – the damage had been done.” (p. 192) She

also detects a suspicious similarity between many examples of modernist urban plans and the Roman camp. She denounces a.o. José-Luis Sert's plan for Barcelona, Ludwig Hilberseimer's superblocks for the replanning of Chicago and Kiyonori Kikutake's City of the Future, which she blames for its fascist character.

She states that the orthogonal archetype also has a very successful derivative: the orthogonal-linear plan of the merchant cities. This plan is, like the orthogonal-connective plan, based on the idea of communication. Moholy-Nagy clearly distinguishes between traffic and communication:

“Traffic is a system of transferring people and goods through a given area by the shortest distance between origin and destination. Its planning is indifferent to the character of the area traversed or to the effect traffic has upon it. (...) Communication, on the other hand, refers to the interconnection of human activities by means of streets and plazas. Their layout, connectedness, and delimiting architecture influence the life of people by providing a designed framework, qualified by tradition and aesthetics. In modern cities both traffic and communication exist side by side, but it is the communication plan that makes a particular city specific and memorable.”

She mentions as examples the Ramblas of Barcelona, Piccadilly in London, the Champs Elysées in Paris and the Copacabana in Rio. She moreover stresses the fact that “the orthogonal-linear merchant city gained ascendancy over all other planning concepts because it offered participation in the drive for power to the majority.” This type of city is not the power symbol for a monarch, nor does it solely derive from the most profitable allotment of the land. It rather fuses architecture, communication and real estate values into a self-conscious expression of an open, outside-oriented community.

In the next chapter, Moholy-Nagy discusses “Clusters and the end of origins”. According to her the whole idea of clusters, and by extension the idea of satellite development, is anti-urban and tends to isolate certain social groups. Between the urban mobility of the city and the land attachment characteristic for the village, the cluster makes up for a third area of human settlement, “where the sharp artificial city lights and the diffused rural moon mix in a twilight zone”. “City satellites”, according to her, “are clusters of buildings that belong neither to the city nor to the village, partaking of the open land and vestiges of nature, but dependent on an imitation of city life for survival.” (p. 241) Although such exurban clusters have existed since the beginning of cities, it is mainly since the beginning of the 20th

century and the environmental ideals of Howard and Unwin that the cluster has been invested with architectural pedigree and thus began to threaten the healthy continuation of a sincere city sense. Weimar Germany elaborated in the Weissenhofsiedlung of Mies van der Rohe and in the Frankfurt Siedlungen of Ernst May the cluster idea, and it thus became the prototype for numerous New Towns and suburbs. But most disastrous, she thinks, was the influence of Le Corbusier's work as a city planner. This work has a peculiar logic and continuity that encompasses in one lifetime the genesis of the cluster concept. His first city plan – the "City for Three Million People" – was concentric in approach. Later he experimented with linearity in the plans for Heliopolis and Rio de Janeiro – really the beginning of his dispersion of the historical city. His third and final step in the philosophy of urbanism was his conception of the Unité d'Habitation. For Sibyl Moholy-Nagy it is clear that there were "two driving motivations, which one might call obsessions, behind the step-by-step genesis of Le Corbusier's urbanism". These were "The Ideal Social Norm" and "The Destruction of the City". The Ideal Social Norm refers to the families that would inhabit Le Corbusier's "Vertical Villages": "According to his highly poetic description, the family would assemble fifty or sixty stories above ground around the hearth as in olden times: the mother would prepare the meal, and the father would survey the unspoiled landscape from a 6-foot-wide loggia, which 'Socrates would have envied.'" (p. 273) The other motivation is his rejection of the city as an essential historical factor. "The target of Le Corbusier was the liquidation of the city as a compound social and architectural entity. Throughout his professional life, he worked tirelessly on the elimination of the ligaments that held the urban body together."

The point for her is that these targets are more than private and harmless obsessions, for "the influence of Le Corbusier was world-wide and decided the fate of city planning in the twentieth century" (p. 275) "Le Corbusier's fluctuating experimental exploration became universal prototypes, losing in the process of popularization those features that had counterbalanced their urban destructiveness: relationship of building to open ground, designed elevation, coloristic and textural variations in open loggias, and –to him most important– the roof terrace with the greatest possible freedom of sculptural form and recreational variety." (p. 279)

Throughout the book, Moholy-Nagy stresses the importance of factors such as landscape, regional climate, tradition, culture and form. She repeatedly refers to the city as a symbol, a symbol not only of power, but also of human aspiration and participa-

tion. The city for her is a generative force, capable of molding people and civilizations, bringing forth creative energies and interconnectedness. Hence her criticism of the modern urbanism of CIAM develops along several lines. First she claims that the idea of clusters, which this urbanism favours, is dissolving the city as such. Second she thinks that many of the master plans of visionary architects come forth from their appropriating to themselves a suprahuman power as matrix makers of common man, denying any claim of participation from the latter. By relying upon the rigidity and uniformity of the orthogonal-modular plan they often exert a coercive power which annihilates the possibilities of participation from the citizens. Third she argues that there is a distinction between traffic and communication, and that the CIAM-doctrine takes traffic into account without paying attention to communication. A most interesting feature in this respect is what she calls 'architectural urbanity'. The term refers to the idea that urbanity is not a matter of a two-dimensional lay-out of streets and axes, but rather results from the interplay of three dimensions – the buildings along the streets and squares being a decisive element.

Architectural urbanity indeed is what according to her is lacking in a city like Brasilia. For the urban spaces in this city are so overdimensioned that they are not apt for communication: the buildings that surround them can barely give form and meaning to these vast spaces (an argument which James Holston will repeat later in a more elaborate way in his book on Brasilia). She blames moreover Costa and Niemeyer for their disregard of ordinary people. In a letter drafted to André Wogenscky (March 3, 1963), she sums up her indignation:

"My violent objection is directed against (...) the attitude taken by Costa and Niemeyer towards the main population of this new city. (...) Ever since Le Corbusier assumed for himself and the city planner the right to design a town in the most rigid framework, people have been deprived of their right to shape their environment by the age-old process of trial and error. Costa is a devout Le Corbusier disciple, and what Le Corbusier said about Bogota could have been said by him: "48 hours after I had arrived in Bogota, the whole life of future generations had been laid down in all detail."

In the lovely little book on Mme. Marta's sculpture occurs the sentence: "Dans la vie, équilibre rompu égale mort." Costa and Niemeyer have deliberately destroyed the equilibrium between the citizen and the city presentation, between the citizen and his urban environment, between the city itself and nature around it. A prisoner cannot find solace

in his prison by the thought that some future group of inmates will be desperate enough to break down the walls."

This argument is remarkably similar to the one that Marshall Berman makes a quarter of a century later, in the preface to the second edition of his book *All That Is Solid Melts Into Air. The Experience of Modernity*. In this book he defines modernism in a very broad way as "any attempt by modern men and women to become subjects as well as objects of modernization, to get a grip on the modern world and make themselves at home in it." (p.5) In the 1988 preface he reflects upon the clash of modernisms he experienced when visiting Brasilia and commenting on the city. He was very critical of the city, pointing out that "Brasilia's design might have made perfect sense for the capital of a military dictatorship, ruled by generals who wanted the people kept at a distance, kept apart and kept down." (p. 7) As the capital of a democracy, however, he considered it a scandal, for it provided no democratic public spaces where people can come and assemble freely from all over the country, to talk to each other and address their government. His criticism was not taken lightly, and Niemeyer responded, Berman recalls, with indignation, indicating that Berman seemed to forget that Brasilia was conceived and planned as the embodiment of the democratic hopes of the Brazilian people and of their desire for modernity. Here you had a clash of modernisms: Berman's one stressing the ideas of openness, communication and flexibility, versus Niemeyer's one who saw the desire for modernity embodied in buildings and spaces that were prime examples of a very specific modernist aesthetics without living up, however, to what Berman expected from modernism in the broader sense.

In Sibyl Moholy-Nagy's work, one might say, a similar clash of modernisms is being acted out. The whole set-up of her intellectual convictions is immersed by her being part of the avant-garde in Weimar Germany and by the legacy of Laszlo Moholy-Nagy's teachings. She subscribes to the ideal of a universal, cosmopolitan humanity that would be liberated by the forces of intellectual freedom, democratic openness and aesthetic experimentations, stressing at the same time – like Berman does – the importance of not losing the connection with the past, with tradition, with culture, with landscape and climate. On the other hand she thinks that certain tendencies within modernist architecture and urbanism go against the grain of this ideal, because they embody a will to power from the part of their architects which is not compatible with the democratic desire of citizens to collectively give form to their cities and which does not take into account

the values of tradition, landscape and climate. The bottomline of her discourse on the city seems to be that really great cities do come forth from a collective desire for the city, a desire that is recognizable as well in a series of of specific and well-considered design decisions as in the long-term historical process in which the inhabitants themselves can take part in the making of their city, without being coerced in a pre-conceived model that wouldn't allow for any variation or new input. For her clearly New York was such a city, Brasilia sadly was not.

KEYWORDS

Sibyl Moholy-Nagy; modern city; urban history; utopia

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